

A COMPREHENSIVE EXPLORATION FOR MANAGING RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS WITH MEDICINAL PLANTS

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Abstract

Background: Autoimmunity occurs when the immune system mistakenly attacks self-antigens, leading to chronic diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis (RA). RA is an autoimmune disorder characterized by inflammation, immune cell infiltration, and synovial membrane damage, ultimately resulting in cartilage degradation and joint destruction. Although steroidal and non-steroidal allopathic treatments are available, they provide only temporary relief by reducing pain and inflammation without curing or preventing disease progression. Furthermore, long-term use of these treatments is associated with severe side effects, highlighting the need for alternative therapeutic approaches.

Methodology: A comprehensive literature review was conducted using databases such as PubMed, ResearchGate, and Google Scholar. Keywords including “rheumatoid arthritis” and “plants for rheumatoid arthritis” were utilized to identify relevant studies on plant-based treatments for RA. Various medicinal plants with ethnobotanical and ethnomedicinal significance were analyzed for their potential therapeutic benefits in managing RA symptoms.

Results: Several medicinal plants with anti-rheumatoid arthritis properties were identified and reviewed for their pharmacological effects. These plants exhibit anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and analgesic properties, which may help alleviate RA symptoms and slow disease progression. Additionally, experimental models used to evaluate the effects of plant-based treatments on RA were examined, providing insights into their mechanisms of action.

Conclusion: Plant-based therapies present promising alternatives to conventional RA treatments by offering potential benefits with fewer adverse effects. The findings from this review highlight the need for further research to explore the efficacy and safety of these natural approaches, paving the way for the development of safer and more effective RA treatments.

Keywords: *Arthritis, Autoimmunity, AYUSH, Immunological disorder*

Introduction

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic autoimmune disorder that primarily affects the joints, leading to inflammation, pain, and progressive joint damage. It affects approximately 0.5–1% of the global population, making it one of the most common autoimmune diseases worldwide. In India, the prevalence of arthritis is significantly higher, with over 20% of the population suffering from various forms of the disease.¹ RA occurs when the immune system mistakenly attacks synovial tissues, resulting in persistent inflammation and joint deterioration. If left untreated, it can cause severe disability, reduced quality of life, and systemic complications involving the cardiovascular, pulmonary, and nervous systems.² The exact cause of RA remains unclear, but it is influenced by genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors. Genetic predisposition plays a crucial role, with specific human leukocyte antigen (HLA) gene variants, such as HLA-DR4 and HLA-DR1, increasing the risk. Other contributing factors include age, hormonal imbalances, infections, and environmental triggers. Smoking is a well-known risk factor that not only increases susceptibility to RA but also worsens disease severity. Additionally, stress and dietary habits may influence immune regulation and RA progression.³

Conventional RA treatments aim to manage symptoms and slow disease progression. These include non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), corticosteroids, disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs), and biologic agents. While these therapies help control inflammation and immune overactivity, they do not offer a permanent cure and often lead to side effects, such as gastrointestinal issues, cardiovascular risks, liver toxicity, and immune

suppression.⁴ Consequently, there is growing interest in alternative approaches for RA management. Medicinal plants have emerged as potential therapeutic agents for RA due to their anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties. Traditional medicine systems like Ayurveda, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), and Unani have long utilized plant-based remedies for autoimmune conditions. Herbs such as *Curcuma longa* (turmeric), *Boswellia serrata* (Indian frankincense), *Withania somnifera* (ashwagandha), *Zingiber officinale* (ginger), and *Tinospora cordifolia* (guduchi) contain bioactive compounds that exhibit significant anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities. Experimental models, such as collagen-induced arthritis (CIA) in mice and adjuvant-induced arthritis (AIA) in rats, are widely used to study RA pathology and evaluate herbal treatments. These models help researchers assess the mechanisms of action, safety, and efficacy of phytochemicals targeting inflammatory pathways, such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β). Despite promising findings, further research is necessary to establish the clinical efficacy and safety of medicinal plants for RA treatment. Standardization, dosage optimization, and large-scale trials are essential for integrating these remedies into mainstream medicine. Combining traditional herbal medicine with modern therapeutic approaches may lead to improved RA management and enhanced patient outcomes.⁵

Causes

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is primarily considered an autoimmune disorder, although its exact cause and etiology remain unknown. The disease occurs when the immune system mistakenly attacks the body's own synovial tissues, leading to chronic inflammation and joint damage. RA is significantly more common in females, with women being three times more likely to develop the condition than men. In severe cases, RA can extend beyond the joints, causing systemic inflammation in the lungs, pleura, sclera, and other organs. Nodular lesions, particularly in subcutaneous tissues, are also common in advanced stages of the disease.⁶ Autoimmunity plays a crucial role in disease progression, making it a major prognostic factor. The inflammation in synovial joints is driven by immune-mediated compounds, including pro-inflammatory cytokines and autoantibodies such as rheumatoid factor (RF) and anti-citrullinated protein antibodies (ACPAs). These immune responses lead to the destruction of articular cartilage and erosion of bone structures, which are the primary pathological features of RA. Although the precise triggers remain unclear, factors such as genetic predisposition, environmental influences, infections, and hormonal imbalances are believed to contribute to disease onset. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for developing targeted therapeutic strategies to manage and potentially prevent RA.⁷

Symptoms

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) presents with a range of symptoms that primarily affect the joints but can also impact overall health. Common symptoms include joint pain, swelling, stiffness (especially in the morning or after inactivity), fatigue, sleep disturbances, unintended weight loss, and flu-like symptoms. The disease typically affects multiple joints symmetrically, with the wrists, knees, and small joints of the hands and feet being most commonly involved. In individuals with RA, abnormal immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies have been detected in the blood. These antibodies trigger an immune response by reacting with antigens, leading to the formation of antigen-antibody complexes. This process results in chronic inflammation, pain, and progressive damage to the synovial membrane. Over time, persistent inflammation can cause joint deformities and functional impairment, significantly affecting the quality of life. Recognizing these symptoms early is crucial for timely diagnosis and effective disease management.⁹

Diagnosis

The diagnosis of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) involves a combination of clinical evaluation, imaging techniques, and laboratory tests. Laboratory assessments typically include tests for anemia, the presence of rheumatoid factor (RF), antibodies against cyclic citrullinated peptides (anti-CCP), and elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) or C-reactive protein (CRP), which indicate inflammation. Clinically, prolonged joint stiffness and pain, especially in the morning or after periods of inactivity, can provide early indications of RA. Imaging techniques such as X-rays help detect joint damage, but they may not be effective in distinguishing early-stage arthritis. More advanced imaging methods like magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and ultrasound are often used to assess disease progression, detect early inflammatory changes, and evaluate joint damage more accurately. Despite these diagnostic tools, there is no single

definitive test for RA. Diagnosis is typically based on a combination of clinical symptoms, laboratory findings, and imaging results to confirm the presence and severity of the disease. Early detection is crucial for initiating appropriate treatment and preventing long-term joint damage.¹⁰

General Treatment for Rheumatoid Arthritis and Its Limitations

The primary goals of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) treatment include pain management, reducing inflammation, and preventing long-term joint damage. The most commonly used medications for RA include disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). These drugs help alleviate symptoms and slow disease progression, but they do not provide a permanent cure. Corticosteroids, which mimic anti-inflammatory hormones naturally released by the adrenal glands, are also widely used to control RA-related inflammation. An ideal corticosteroid should be effective at low doses while minimizing adverse effects.¹¹ However, both steroidal and non-steroidal drugs only manage symptoms and do not halt the progression of the disease. Long-term use of these medications poses significant health risks. Prolonged steroid use can lead to severe side effects, including kidney, liver, and cardiovascular complications. Patients may also experience short-term adverse effects such as nausea, infections, allergic reactions, and respiratory issues. These limitations highlight a major drawback in RA treatment, as conventional medications primarily target symptom relief rather than addressing the root cause of the disease. While these therapies help manage pain, inflammation, and swelling, they fail to provide a definitive cure, necessitating the exploration of alternative treatment strategies for more effective and holistic RA management.¹²

Ayurvedic Perspective of Rheumatoid Arthritis

Ayurveda, a traditional system of medicine, is based on the balance of three fundamental energies known as doshas: Vata, Pitta, and Kapha. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) shares similarities with an Ayurvedic condition called Amavata. Amavata is linked to the accumulation of Ama—a toxic, undigested metabolic byproduct—in the gut due to impaired digestion. This toxic buildup triggers inflammation and disrupts the balance of Vata in the body. According to Ayurveda, individuals with dominant Vata dosha are more prone to developing Amavata. To counteract this condition, Ayurveda recommends dietary modifications, including whole grains, legumes, leafy vegetables, and buttermilk. Spices such as ginger, garlic, and turmeric are advised due to their anti-inflammatory and digestive properties. Lukewarm water aids digestion, and ginger-infused water is often used to eliminate toxins. Several medicinal plants with anti-arthritis potential have been traditionally used, as summarized¹²⁻⁵⁶ in Table 1.

The Need for Natural Remedies

Since ancient times, natural remedies have played a crucial role in managing diseases. Many indigenous communities and traditional medicine practitioners still rely on herbal treatments. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), nearly 80% of the global population depends on plant-based medicines. Herbal remedies are commonly consumed as infusions, extracts, or raw formulations. Many observations suggest that incorporating medicinal plants into daily diets can significantly improve disease symptoms. This highlights the vast potential of phytochemicals in treating RA.

Possible Mechanism of Action of Herbal Drugs

Several studies have explored how herbal drugs counteract RA at the molecular level. Since RA progresses through multiple pathways, herbal medicines often exhibit multi-targeted effects. One key mechanism involves toll-like receptors (TLRs), which play a major role in RA-related inflammation. TLR activation triggers the nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) pathway, leading to the production of inflammatory mediators such as inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), and interleukin-6 (IL-6). This results in increased production of prostaglandin E2 (PGE2), leading to leukocyte proliferation, joint inflammation, and cartilage destruction. Thus, inhibiting NF- κ B is considered a promising therapeutic strategy for RA. Additionally, cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), IL-1 β , and IL-6 contribute to disease progression by activating collagenase and other proteases, which degrade cartilage. These cytokines also promote immune cell infiltration into synovial joints, exacerbating inflammation. Herbal drugs that inhibit these pathways can help mitigate RA symptoms. Medicinal plants which have been tested experimentally and proven their efficacy are represented in tabular form⁵⁷⁻⁹¹ in Table 2.

Medicinal Plants with Anti-Rheumatoid Arthritis Potential

Several plants have demonstrated significant anti-inflammatory effects in experimental models of RA: *Saraca asoca*: Traditionally used for RA, this plant has shown potent anti-inflammatory properties by reducing pro-inflammatory cytokine levels. *Ocimum* species (Tulsi): Exhibits anti-inflammatory activity through the inhibition of arachidonic acid metabolism and histamine release. Eugenol, a bioactive compound in *Ocimum*, plays a key role in its therapeutic effects. *Cannabis sativa*: Contains cannabidiol (CBD), which inhibits COX-2 and exhibits strong anti-inflammatory effects in RA models. *Cassia* species: Aerial parts of *Cassia* plants have been shown to reduce joint swelling, cartilage degradation, and immune cell infiltration in experimental arthritis models. *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger): Contains 6-gingerol, which blocks NF- κ B and protein kinase C (PKC) pathways, reducing inflammation. *Semecarpus anacardium*: A tree native to the sub-Himalayan region with antioxidant properties. It inhibits reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and reduces TNF- α and nitric oxide (NO) levels, preventing synovial damage. *Artemisia absinthium* (Wormwood): Reduces inflammation by inhibiting NO and PGE2 synthesis. Scoparone, a bioactive compound in *Artemisia*, blocks COX-2 expression, alleviating RA symptoms. *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric): Curcumin, its primary bioactive compound, inhibits phospholipase activity, reduces MMP-3 expression, and prevents IL-1 β -induced collagen degradation. *Moringa oleifera*: Lowers serum levels of rheumatoid factor (RF) and pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1 β . *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* (Night-flowering jasmine): Reduces IL-1 and TNF- α levels in blood serum, decreasing inflammation. *Swertia chirayita*: Down regulates pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IL-6, showing potential in experimental arthritis models. The minimal side effects of these herbal remedies make them a promising alternative to conventional RA treatments. Many of these plants are currently under scientific investigation to validate their efficacy and develop standardized herbal formulations.

Conclusion

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic autoimmune disorder characterized by joint inflammation, pain, and deformities. Conventional treatments, including disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs), non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), and corticosteroids, provide symptomatic relief but do not offer a permanent cure. Additionally, long-term use of these medications is associated with significant side effects. Given these limitations, herbal medicine presents a promising alternative for RA management. Traditional knowledge, backed by modern scientific research, highlights the potential of medicinal plants in alleviating RA symptoms and modulating disease progression. Currently, over 450 plant species have been identified for their anti-arthritic properties. Many of these herbal remedies demonstrate anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and antioxidant effects with minimal side effects, making them a viable complementary therapy. The integration of herbal treatments into mainstream medicine could revolutionize RA management, providing safer and more sustainable therapeutic options. Ongoing research on the phytochemicals present in these plants continues to validate their efficacy, paving the way for future advancements in natural RA treatment.

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Table 1: Traditionally Used Plants for Treating Rheumatoid Arthritis

Name of Plant	Part Used	Mode of Use	Function
<i>Alpinia galangal</i>	Rhizomes	Paste of rhizome taken orally	Provides relief from pain
<i>Anacyclus pyrethrum</i>	Roots	Infusion drink taken like tea	Anti-rheumatic & anti-arthritic
<i>Aphanamixis polystachya</i>	Bark	Oil applied on joints	Acts as an analgesic
<i>Aquilaria agallocha</i>	Wood	Decoction taken; oil applied on joints	Relieves pain and inflammation
<i>Argemone mexicana</i>	Whole plant, Latex	Oil applied to affected areas	Treats rheumatologic conditions
<i>Callicarpa macrophylla</i>	Flowers, Fruits	Decoction taken orally	Anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antipyretic
<i>Capparis decidua</i>	Roots	Powder or infusion taken orally	Treats rheumatism and fever
<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i>	Roots	Oil applied; powder taken orally	Treats joint infections caused by pathogens
<i>Carthamus tinctorium</i>	Seeds	Infusion taken orally	Anti-inflammatory and analgesic
<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Fruits	Infusion or fruit paste taken orally	Analgesic
<i>Catunaregum spinosa</i>	Bark	Paste or oil applied to affected area	Useful in rheumatism
<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i>	Roots	Powder of fruit taken orally	Anti-inflammatory
<i>Commiphora myrrha</i>	Gum	Oil applied; gum taken orally	Relieves pain
<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	Leaves	Taken orally or as an infusion	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Cordia dichotoma</i>	Fruits	Taken orally or in powder form	Anti-rheumatic
<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	Fruits, Leaves	Taken orally	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Euphorbia nerifolia</i>	Leaf	Taken as juice orally	Relieves pain in rheumatism
<i>Euphorbia ligularia</i>	Whole plant	Taken as juice or infusion	Used in the treatment of rheumatism
<i>Ficus bengalensis</i>	Latex	Taken as juice	Used in the treatment of rheumatism
<i>Fritillaria roylei</i>	Bulbs	Taken as powder or juice	Used in the treatment of rheumatism
<i>Glycosmis arborea</i>	Roots	Taken as powder	Useful in the treatment of arthritis
<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i>	Leaves	Taken as powder, juice, or infusion	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	Whole plant	Oil applied externally for joint pain; other parts taken in powder form	Effective for joint inflammations
<i>Hiptage bengalensis</i>	Barks, Leaves, Flowers	Taken as powder	Treatment of chronic rheumatism
<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i>	Barks, Seeds, Leaves	Taken as powder	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i>	Roots, Leaves, Seeds	Taken as powder	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Hyoscyamus niger</i>	Leaves, Seeds	Taken as powder	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Illicium verum</i>	Fruits	Taken as powder or juice	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Inula racemosa</i>	Roots	Taken orally as powder	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Ipomoea cairica</i>	Seeds	Oil applied for pain relief	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Jasminum lanceolarium</i>	Leaves, Flowers	Taken as powder or juice	Effective against rheumatism and fever; anti-inflammatory
<i>Jatropha curcas</i>	Oil	Oil applied externally for joint pain	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Juglans regia</i>	Fruits	Taken as powder or juice	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Justicia gendarussa</i>	Roots, Leaves	Taken as powder or juice	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Kaempferia galangal</i>	Rhizomes, Leaves	Taken orally in powder form or juice	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Lantana camara</i>	Fruits	Taken orally	Traditionally used for the treatment of RA
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	Leaves	Taken orally in powder form or infusion	Used in arthritic disorder
<i>Lilium polyphyllum</i>	Bulb	Taken orally in powder form or infusion	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>	Oil	Oil used externally for joint pain	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Roots, Bark	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Whole plant	Taken orally	Helps to deal with rheumatoid arthritis symptoms
<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Fruits	Taken orally in different forms or as juice	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Myxopyrum serratum</i>	Leaves	Taken in powdered form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Naravelia zeylanica</i>	Whole plant	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Nilgiranthus ciliatus</i>	Roots	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	Whole plant	Taken as infusion, powder, or leaves eaten raw orally	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Oroxylum indicum</i>	Roots	Taken in powder form	Possesses anti-inflammatory activity
<i>Pandanus odoratissimus</i>	Oil	Oil used externally for joint pain	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Piper betel</i>	Whole plant	Taken orally in powdered form	Effective in inflammation treatment
<i>Piper nigrum</i>	Fruits	Used raw in cooking or taken in powdered form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Plumeria rubra</i>	Milky juice	Applied externally to relieve pain	Effective in inflammation treatment
<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Leaves	Taken in powder form	Helps in painful rheumatic joints
<i>Premna corymbosa</i>	Leaves	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Premna serratifolia</i>	Whole plant	Taken orally	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties

<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Leaves	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>	Roots	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Ruta chalepensis</i>	Oil	Oil used externally for joint pain	Analgesic, antipyretic, anti-inflammatory, and relieves rheumatic pain
<i>Sida cordifolia</i>	Roots, Leaves	Taken in powder form	Used for treating rheumatism
<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	Whole plant	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Spondias pinnata</i>	Roots	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain, anti-inflammatory, and helps in muscular pain in rheumatism
<i>Stereospermum colais</i>	Leaves	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Tectona grandis</i>	Wood	Taken in powder form, oil used externally	Used in treating inflammatory swelling
<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>	Fruits	Taken in powder or juice form of fresh fruit	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	Whole plant	Used externally for joint pain	Used for external application in rheumatic-arthritis
<i>Vateria indica</i>	Oil	Oil used externally for joint pain	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Roots	Taken in powder form	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Stem	Taken in powder form or infusion	Relieves pain and has anti-inflammatory properties

Table 2: Experimentally Proven Plants for Rheumatoid Arthritis

Name of the Plant	Common Name	Type of Extract Used	Activity Observed
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Apamaraga	Ethanol	Prevented the recruitment of leukocytes
<i>Aconitum vilmorinianum</i>	Wolf's-bane	Ethanol	Improvement of joint swelling and vascular permeability
<i>Ajuga bracteosa</i>	Ground pine	Ethanol	COX-1 and COX-2 inhibition
<i>Ajuga decumbens</i>	Bugle weed	Ethanol	Regulates balance between bone formation and resorption
<i>Alstonia boonei</i>	Cheese wood	Methanol	Relief in early and late phase of pain
<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	Devil tree	Ethanol	Reduction of total leukocyte, lymphocytes, and monocyte migration
<i>Ammania gracifera</i>	Tooth cup	Aqueous, Alcoholic, Petroleum Ether, Chloroform, Methanol	Decrease in ESR and WBC count
<i>Aristolochia bracteata</i>	Kidamari	Petroleum Ether, Chloroform, Methanol	Maintains vascular permeability, synovial membrane integrity, and inhibits cytokines & leukotriene infiltration
<i>Argyrea speciosa</i>	Elephant Creeper	Methanol, Ethanol	Prevented the recruitment of leukocytes
<i>Arisaema rhizomatum</i>	Jack in the Pulpit	Methanol	Results against proinflammatory cytokines and RA factor secretion
<i>Arnebia euchroma</i>	Pink Arnebia	Ethanol (95%)	Suppression of IL-1 β and TNF- α levels
<i>Artocarpus tonkinensis</i>	Chay	Ethyl acetate	Apoptosis induction in activated T-cells
<i>Asystasia dalzelliana</i>	Violet Asystasia	Ethanol	Decreasing synthesis/release of T-cell mediators
<i>Baccharis genistelloides</i>	Carqueja	Aqueous	Suppresses synovial fibroblast proliferation and induced production of progelatinase B and PGE2
<i>Bacopa monniera</i>	Herpestis Monniera	Methanol	Stabilizing action on lysosomal membranes
<i>Barleria lupulina</i>	Hophead	Methanol	Assisting cell mediated immune responses
<i>Barleria prionitis</i>	Katsareya	Hydro-ethanolic	Lowers the ESR level and has immuno-modulatory activity
<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	Kachnar	Ethanol	Alteration in antioxidant enzymes such as catalase, superoxide dismutase, and glutathione peroxidase
<i>Caesalpinia sappan</i>	Sapanwood	Ethanol	Showed inhibitory expression of TNF- α and pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β
<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	Milkweed	Petroleum Ether	Pro-inflammatory cytokines are reduced
<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Sodom apple	Methanol	Inhibit cellular influx and vascular permeability
<i>Caltha palustris</i>	Kingcup	Methanol	Absolute count and percentage of splenic T-regulatory cells CD4+CD25+FOXP3 was reduced
<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Ganja	Alcoholic	Diminished IFN- γ production
<i>Caesalpinia sappan</i>	Sapanwood	Ethanol	Showed inhibitory expression of TNF- α and pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β
<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	Milkweed	Petroleum Ether	Pro-inflammatory cytokines are reduced
<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Sodom apple	Methanol	Inhibit cellular influx and vascular permeability
<i>Caltha palustris</i>	Kingcup	Methanol	Absolute count and percentage of splenic T-regulatory cells CD4+CD25+FOXP3 was reduced
<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Ganja	Alcoholic	Diminished IFN- γ production
<i>Capparis erythrocarpus</i>	Flamingo	Ethanol	Inhibit the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines
<i>Capparis spinosa</i>	Flinders rose	Hydro-alcoholic	Counteract the effects of IL-1
<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i>	Balloon plant	Ethanol CFA	Histamine and prostaglandin synthesis inhibition
<i>Cayaponia tayuya</i>	Tayuya	Hydro-alcoholic	Modify the expression of both COX-2 and nitric oxide synthase-2;

			decreases production of IL-1 β & TNF- α in lymphocytes Reduction of CRP and RF levels in the serum
<i>Cassia uniflora</i>	One leaf senna	Methanol, Petroleum Ether, Ethyl Acetate	
<i>Celastrus aculeatus</i>	Gua shan fena	Ethanol CFA	Down regulate the biochemical and immunological mediator
<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Brahmi	Methanol	Have inhibitory activity against protein denaturation and membrane stabilization
<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i>	Dalchini	Aqueous	Inhibition of leukocyte emigration
<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>	Butua	50% aqueous:ethanol	Acid phosphatase and N-acetyl glucosaminidase were reduced while hexose and sialic acid increased
<i>Chelidonium majus</i>	Tetterwort	Methanol	Decreased number of CD4+T cells in lymph node and spleen, immunosuppression by lowering the CD4+T-cells and enhance CD8+T-cells
<i>Cleome gynandra</i>	Shone cabbage	Ethanol CFA	Modifying the lysosomal membrane thus inhibiting lysosomal enzymes release
<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	Cilantro	Hydro-alcoholic	Inhibit the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines including TNF- α
<i>Costus speciosus</i>	Keukand	Methanol	Suppression of inflammatory mediators
<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Turmeric	n-Hexane	Activation of genes critical to articular inflammation
<i>Curcuma zedoaria</i>	White turmeric	Chloroform, Petroleum Ether	Decrease the latency time to explore
<i>Ephedra sinica</i>	Ma Haung	Aqueous	Expressions of TNF- α and IL-6 genes restored to normal levels in experimental arthritis
<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i>	Antique spurge	Methanol	Arachidonic metabolites and cell-mediated immunity was suppressed
<i>Ficus bengalensis</i>	Banyan tree	Methanol	Inhibition of the early phase of inflammation
<i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	Maiden hair tree	Methanol	Macrophages infiltrated to the inflamed site was inhibited for NO production
<i>Glycosmis pentaphylla</i>	Orange berry	Ethanol	Increased haematological parameters like RBC count, Hb level and the ESR
<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Liquorice	Methanol	Lysosomal membrane stability increased and inhibiting leukocyte migration
<i>Hedera helix</i>	European ivy	Ethanol, hydro-ethanolic	Reduction in arthritic symptoms
<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	Indian Sarsaparilla	Hydro-ethanolic	Inhibition of bradykinin, carrageenan, and serotonin in inflammation
<i>Hippocratea excelsa</i>	Mata piojo	Ethanol	Active against both proliferative and exudative phases of inflammation
<i>Hybanthus enneaspermus</i>	Humpback flower	Aqueous, Ethanol	Inhibits pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , TNF- α) and decreases GM-CSF, PDGF, and IFN- γ production
<i>Justicia gendarussa</i>	Willow-leaved justice	Ethanol	Inhibition of leukocyte migration
<i>Lantana camara</i>	-	Ethanol	Lipoxygenase and/or cyclooxygenase inhibition
<i>Laportea bulbifera</i>	Mukago-irakusa	Ethanol	Decreased IFN- γ and IL-2, increased IL-10 and TGF- β
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	Henna	70% aqueous ethyl alcohol	Decrease in inflammatory mediators, suppressing acute and chronic inflammation
<i>Leucas aspera</i>	Thumbai	n-Hexane, Chloroform, Ethyl Acetate, Ethanol	Decreased CRP, TNF- α , and IL-2; complete cartilage formation
<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>	Flax	Petroleum Ether	Inhibitory effect on arachidonate metabolism
<i>Lonicera japonica</i>	Japanese honeysuckle	Methanol	Suppresses T-cell proliferation
<i>Merremia emarginata</i>	Kupit-kupit	Ethanol	Restores body weight, improves ESR and hemoglobin values
<i>Operculina turpethum</i>	Turpeth	Ethanol	Inhibit the denaturation of proteins
<i>Panax ginseng</i>	Ginseng	Ethanol	Suppressed TPA-induced acute inflammation
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Chanca	Aqueous	ALT and IT levels were reduced
<i>Physalis angulata</i>	Fisalia	Aqueous, Ethanol, Methanol	Inhibit the denaturation of proteins
<i>Pinus maritime</i>	Maritime pine	Hydro-ethanolic	Inhibits acute and chronic inflammatory lesions
<i>Piper betle</i>	Tambula	Hydro-ethanolic	Reduced levels of CD4+T cell specific IFN- γ in splenocytes
<i>Piper longum</i>	Pippali	Aqueous	Neutrophils adherence to endothelial monolayer was inhibited
<i>Pisonia grandis</i>	Devil's-claws	Ethanol	IFN, GM-CSF and PGDF cytokines are suppressed
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i>	Water lettuce	Aqueous, Ethanol	Low levels of C-reactive proteins and ESR
<i>Saussurea lappa</i>	Kuth	Ethanol	TNF- α release was inhibited
<i>Operculina turpethum</i>	Turpeth	Ethanol	Inhibit the denaturation of proteins
<i>Panax ginseng</i>	Ginseng	Ethanol	Suppressed TPA-induced acute inflammation
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Chanca	Aqueous	ALT and IT levels were reduced
<i>Physalis angulate</i>	Fisalia	Aqueous, Ethanol, Methanol	Inhibit the denaturation of proteins
<i>Pinus maritime</i>	Maritime pine	Hydro-ethanolic	Inhibits acute and chronic inflammatory lesions
<i>Piper betle</i>	Tambula	Hydro-ethanolic	Reduced levels of CD4+T cell specific IFN- γ in splenocytes
<i>Piper longum</i>	Pippali	Aqueous	Inhibits neutrophils adherence, ICAM-1, VCAM-1, NF-kB

<i>Pisonia grandis</i>	Devil's-claws	Ethanol	Suppresses cytokines in CFA-induced mediators
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i>	Water lettuce	Aqueous, Ethanol	Low levels of C-reactive proteins and ESR
<i>Premna serratifolia</i>	Agnimanth	Ethanol	Suppression of migration of leukocytes
<i>Pseudocedrea kotschy</i>	Hard cedar	Aqueous	Reduction in inflammation due to mediators suppression
<i>Punica granatum</i>	Pomegranate	Aqueous	Inhibition of the spectrum of the signal transduction pathway
<i>Rhus verniciflua</i>	Chinese lacquer Tree	n-Hexane	Suppression of inflammatory cytokines and angiogenic factor
<i>Ruta graveolens</i>	Rue	Aqueous	Reduces cell influx, mediators release, lipid peroxidation
<i>Salacia reticulata</i>	Khothala himbutu	Ethanol	Inhibitory effect against IL-1 β activated cell proliferation
<i>Salix nigra</i>	Black willow	Methanol	Inhibition of pro-inflammatory activity
<i>Saraca asoca</i>	Ashoka	Methanol	Stabilizing lysosomal membrane, reducing acid hydrolase release
<i>Saussurea lappa</i>	Kuth	Ethanol	Inhibition of TNF- α release in LPS-stimulated macrophage cells
<i>emecarpus Anacardium</i>	Bhallatak	Aqueous, Ethanol	Inhibition of cytokine production
<i>Sida rhombifolia</i>	Cuban jute	Methanol, Petroleum Ether	Generation of reactive oxygen species was suppressed
<i>Sinomenium acutum</i>	Tudurafuji	Alcoholic	Inhibition of lymphocyte proliferation and macrophage
<i>Torilis japonica</i>	Upright hedge Parsley	Methanol	Inhibitory effects on CD4 T-cells immune cell trafficking
<i>Toxicodendron pubescens</i>	Atlantic poison	Aqueous	Immunosuppressant activity
<i>Trigonella foenum</i>	Fenugreek	Aqueous	Reduces cell influx, mediators release, and oxidative stress
<i>Urtica pilulifera</i>	Roman nettle	Methanol	Suppresses the activation of NF-kB
<i>Vernonia cinerea</i>	Bitter leaf ndole	Ethanol	Membrane stability-modulating effect
<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Indian winter Cherry	Hydro-alcoholic	Inhibiting the release of inflammatory mediators
<i>Xanthium srtuarium</i>	Datura	Ethanol	Inflammatory mediators inhibited, NO level decreased
<i>Yucca schidigera</i>	Spanish dagger	Hydro-alcoholic	Inhibition of NF-kB activation